

PROJECT SUMMARY

THE HYDRO ENERGY SYSTEM OF CENTRAL ASIA: EFFECTS FROM GLACIER RETREAT AND GEOPOLITICS

Polina Lemenkova

Highlights:

1. The climate change impacts hydrological resources of Tian Shan and causes glacier retreat and water shortage.
2. The irregular distribution of water resources in Central Asia leads to conflicts in neighboring countries.
3. The key water providers (Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan) control hydro-energy while water consumers (Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan) depend on it.
4. The negative anthropogenic impacts on hydro resources include ineffective management: outdated economic and agrarian system, water-consuming irrigation

Introduction: geography of Tian Shan.

The Tian Shan is one of the largest high mountain systems and one of the major water supply in Central Asia. The region of Tian Shan basin has colossal geographic resources, unique ecosystems and priceless hydro-energetic resources. The mountains contain 7,590 glaciers with an area of 13,271.45 km². Many rivers originate in these glaciers and snowfields. Intensely taken for hydropower energy production, urban systems, agricultural activities, irrigation and other human needs, river waters are highly important hydrological resource for population. Two major rivers, Amu Daria and Syr Daria, vitally important for the region, originate in Tian Shan and flow to Aral Sea, which has a deep connection with Tian Shan glacier system.

Geopolitical problems and hydro-economics

Geopolitical situation of Tian Shan is difficult: it crosses five densely populated Central Asian countries. Actual problem in the region consists in water resources and usage regulated by regional distribution of hydropower resources and geopolitical questions. Hydropower resources directly affect sustainable development of the politician and economic systems in Central Asia.

The problem of water usage and delivery is an important topic in the energy debates in Central Asia. Tian Shan region can be divided on territories located in the highlands of plateaux (upper lands) with rich hydrological resources and excellent water supply and lowland regions located in the valleys, with water shortage. Thus, the region is clearly divided into 'water-rich' countries (Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan) and 'water-dependent' ones (Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan and Kazakhstan). Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan and Kazakhstan, located in the lowlands of Tian Shan, have lack of water resources and depend on water delivery, while mountain Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan are rich in water resources. The irregular distribution of water resources is the main reason of the hydro-energetic problem in the region. 'Water-rich' countries control almost all hydro-energetic water resources in the region. Thus, Kyrgyzstan majorly controls drainage areas of Syr Darya basin, while Tajikistan – the basin of Amu Darya, the largest, longest and most important river in Central Asia. Other energy resources are also distributed unevenly: Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan have predominant natural gas economy with rich hydrocarbon resources; Kazakhstan has significant oil and gas reserves.

The main water resources in Central Asia are located in Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan, which control major river basins. It is caused by their upper location on Tian Shan plateau. About 60% of the total flow towards Aral Sea is formed in Tajikistan. With the total annual of ca 600B kWh hydro energy production, Tajikistan is the third largest in the world and second in post-Soviet countries after Russia. The hydro-energetic sector of Tajikistan is the most powerful and important for the country's economy: 95% of all energy is taken from hydro-plants (usually not exceeding 10-20 %). Nevertheless, only 10% from the total country runoff is used for internal purposes, while other goes downwards for use by other countries. For example, the Nurek hydro-plant controls ca 40% of water resources needed by Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan. Additionally, Tajikistan has impressive fresh water reserves stored in glaciers (> 60% of Central Asia). Kyrgyzstan generates ca 90% of electricity from the hydro power stations (Naryn River). However, its water resources declined since 1990s due to ineffective management and cross-border water claims among Central Asian states.

The main point of claims from Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan is financial contribution in covering expenses of hydroelectric power production from hydro plants by neighboring countries. The debates focus on prices to maintain hydro-technical infrastructure. Kyrgyzstan considers water as commercial product and plans introducing monetary charge for water in the future with purpose to receive market compensation from other Asian countries for water supply services. However, it can cause high risks of social and political rebels in the region. The commercial paid water usage is the worst idea to be introduced in Central Asia: it could become a heavy burden for simple citizens of Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan. Water shortage will affect hydro-economic sectors of the lower countries significantly: it may cause protests from local agrarian population living in the valleys and strongly depending on water resources. At the same time, the 'hydrocarbon-rich' countries almost totally controlling resources of gas make pressure on Tajikistan

and Kyrgyzstan. This causes conflicts and debates about energy situation among participating countries.

Local Uzbek-Kyrgyz water conflicts happen in Ferghana valley (Uzbekistan). The main claim of Uzbekistan is to provide necessary amount of water for Uzbek agriculture. However, the prices for the water are a point of disagreement. The lack of water in the densely populated Ferghana valley in Uzbekistan is a serious trigger of social rebels, which may arise in case of water deficit or commercial water delivery.

Additional factor for energetic tensions is accelerated development of hydro power energetics. Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan plan to construct several additional hydroelectric power plants under investments from the USA, Pakistan and China. This causes negative reaction of neighbor countries due to possible consequences: constructing huge dams will cause water shortage in the surrounding territories, since large areas upstream will be flooded.

The notable anthropogenic impact on hydro energy situation includes ineffective resource management, i.e. outdated style of economy and agrarian system, ineffective and water-consuming irrigation. Excessive loss of water is caused by old traditional irrigation system, still used in agriculture. The water consumption exceeds 3-10 times the world standards. The transition towards modern agricultural system and sustainable water management would change situation, though the modernization and effective city management requires financial investments.

Climate change problems

Additionally to difficult geopolitical situation, there are impacts of climate change on water resources in Tian Shan area. Global climate warming seriously affects Tian Shan mountainous ecosystems. Increase in air temperature and decrease of precipitation trigger glaciers and snow thaw, the period and intensity of melt. This causes deglaciation and leads to water deficit. Thus, summer floods, needed for Uzbek irrigation, are reduced significantly since last decades.

Other important environmental factor that impacts hydro resources is sand masses carried from Central Asian deserts. The seasonal monsoon winds carry over significant sand and dust masses towards mountain glaciers. They then “settle down” on the ice fields, intensify ice and snow melt and glacier reduction. The melt of Tian Shan glaciers affects ecosystems of Aral Sea, highly vulnerable in semi-desert climate. The Aral Sea suffers from water shortage during last decades, which causes soil salinization, desertification and water shortage. Such consequences of the climate change cause irreversible processes in the sensitive ecosystems of Tian Shan, which has negative effects on hydro-energy resources (drying lakes and rivers, thawing glaciers and snow).

Conclusion and Suggestions

The Central Asian region is one of the most complex regions of the world due to the difficult geopolitical situation, complex boundaries pattern and concentration of densely populated countries with high demand for energy resources.

The project focuses on the environmental analysis of Central Asian energetic system and usage of waters from Tian Shan mountain glaciers. A multidisciplinary analysis of the current work includes: 1) discussion of the geopolitical problems of water supply in Central Asia; 2) analysis of climate impact on hydro-energetic resources in Tian Shan.

The irregular distribution of water resources in Central Asia leads to regional conflicts of interest among key water providers and major customers. As a result, water supply is a point of discussions among neighboring countries. The situation is redoubled by natural factors (climate warming) and anthropogenic aspects. The non-diplomatic, one-sided energy policy of energy-rich countries leads to the difficulties in the geopolitical relationships.

The optimal suggestion is based on the well-balanced sustainable water usage considering interests of all countries. Special attention should be paid to oil and gas resources stored in Caspian Sea basin, a major reservoir for energy. A consensus in the energy use must be observed for all parties, since the oil, gas, hydro and coal resources are distributed irregularly in the region. The inter-governmental argues between the “water-controlling” and “water-consuming” states should be regulated. This would be a major direction for development of hydro energetic system in Central Asia. The governmental decisions should be discussed by all parties. The involvement of independent third parties (foreign) with no interest in local conflicts is advisable: it could assist in solving dubious questions of water energy usage.

The project focuses on critical analysis of the hydro energy in Central Asia. Current problems are caused by the uneven distribution of hydro resources in region, ineffective management of water resources, extensive water use as well as climate impacts. The discussion and overview of the current local problems and tensions are provided.